

HORIZON-CL5-2021-D2-01-08 – GA 101069492

Revolutionary energy storage cycle with carbon free aluminium

D4.2 Experimental results and mathematical model for high temperature Al conversion

Document Information	
Due Date:	30. 06. 2024
Actual Submission Date:	24. 06. 2024
Type of Deliverable (Report/Data/DEC/Ethics):	Report
Dissemination Level (Public/Sensitive)	Public
Prepared By:	Ana Drinčić, Nigel Van de Velde, Franci Merzel and Ivan Jerman
Version:	V1.0

Co-funded by
the European Union

The Swiss contribution is supported by the Swiss State Secretariate for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract number 22.00043

Disclaimer

This document's contents are not intended to replace the consultation of any applicable legal sources or the necessary advice of a legal expert, where appropriate. All information in this document is provided "as is" and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user, therefore, uses the information at its sole risk and liability. For the avoidance of all doubts, the European Commission has no liability in respect of this document, which is merely representing the authors' view.

Foreword

The deliverable report summarises the work in task 4.2, aluminium reactions with water steam at temperatures above 200°C, which were studied at the National Institute of Chemistry in Ljubljana. Aluminium fuel could provide a means of transferring energy across different seasons. Task 4.2 taught us that the reaction between aluminium metal and steam can extract energy from metal on demand. The aforementioned approach could be a solid foundation for the Al-to-energy prototype design proposed in task 4.3. OST and NIC jointly decided to continue working on a low-temperature prototype for T4.3, despite the possibility of designing a pilot prototype at higher temperatures. During the study, researchers used various compositions, shapes, and purity grades of aluminium metals as fuel. As a result, we produced alumina with varying conversion efficiency and phase compositions. We exchanged a larger batch of alumina, consisting of gamma and alpha mixtures, with SINTEF for composition and dissolution studies in cryolite. Such studies enable us to confirm that the produced alumina is suitable for recycling (T5.1).

Dedicated NIC staff performed the work.

- Ana Drinčić: Al discharge studies, alumina studies, report writing;
- Nigel Van de Velde: Al discharge studies, alumina studies, SEM, XRD, report writing;
- Matic Grom: reactor construction, Al discharge studies, hydrogen analysis;
- Helena Spreizer: Al discharge experimental work;
- Franci Merzel: mathematical modelling, report writing;
- Ivan Jerman: Al discharge studies, SEM analysis, report writing, management.

With contributions from Francisco Ruiz-Zepedafor (TEM), Boštjan Genorio (XPS), Tomaž Kotnik (pore size studies), Matjaž Rejc (Anton Paar) (pore size studies).

Table of contents

1.	Executive summary	5
2.	Introduction	6
3.	Materials and methods	9
3.1	Materials used	9
3.1.1	Surface area comparison and porosity evaluation	10
3.1.2	Granules porosity.....	15
3.1.3	Impurities SEM/EDS.....	15
3.2	Reaction setup	21
3.3	Characterization methods	22
3.3.1	SEM/EDS	22
3.3.2	XRD	22
3.3.3	XPS	22
3.3.1	Particle size	22
3.3.2	TEM.....	23
3.3.3	Operando Raman.....	23
3.3.4	Pore size.....	23
4.	Aluminium steam reaction kinetic	24
4.1	Effect of temperature	25
4.2	Effect of pressure.....	29
4.3	Effect of the granule size / surface area	32
4.4	Repeatability.....	33
5.	Alumina composition and recycling feasibility	35
5.1	Surface morphology of products	35
5.2	Alumina article size distribution	38
5.3	Alumina pores evaluation.....	40
5.4	Phase composition.....	40
5.5	TEM.....	43
5.6	Oxidation initiation by steam – XPS analysis	44
5.7	Limitations and pitfalls	47
5.7.1	Uneven material composition	47
5.7.2	Volume increase and reactor blocking	51
6.	Mathematical model	52
7.	Summary and conclusions	54
8.	References	59
Appendix:	62	

Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

α -Al(OH) ₃	gibbsite
β -Al(OH) ₃	bayerite
γ -AlOOH	boehmite
Θ	X-ray incident angle
ψ	structural constant in random pore reaction model
A	pre-exponential factor
Al	aluminium
Al(OH) ₃	aluminium trihydroxide
C	parameter in random pore model related to the Arrhenius equation
C_e	equilibrium concentration
C_r	critical concentration
E_a	activation energy
EDX	energy dispersive X-ray
H ₂	hydrogen
K	reaction rate constant
K_{prec}	precipitation rate constant
NaOH	sodium hydroxide
P	pressure
PSD	particle size distribution
R	universal gas constant
r	reaction rate
R^2	coefficient of determination
SEM	scanning electron microscopy
T	temperature
τ	total reaction time
$t_{50\%}$	reaction time at 50% conversion
$t_{90\%}$	reaction time at 90% conversion
V	volume
XH ₂	fractional hydrogen amount
XRD	X-ray diffraction
OST	Ostschweizer Fachhochschule, Rapperswil, Switzerland
NIC	National Institute of Chemistry, Ljubljana, Slovenia

1. Executive summary

The delivery report D4.2 focused on exploring the reaction features of aluminium-superheated steam at temperatures above 200°C, as well as the evaluation of reaction products. The goal was to determine optimal reaction kinetics for producing heat (exothermic reaction) and electricity (from the production of H₂ in an optional fuel cell) for realising seasonal energy storage system. A comprehensive laboratory setup was developed, including a superheated steam production vessel, nitrogen purging, steam introduction, temperature control, and hydrogen evolution measurement. Regarding the Al-superheated steam reaction, laboratory experiments were performed to evaluate different factors affecting the reaction rate. We used aluminum foil (Al-foil) and different shaped and sized aluminum granules to test the influence of: i) the reaction temperature and pressure; ii) the presence of impurities; and iii) the surface of the aluminum fuels on hydrogen evolution rate. The results evidenced that faster reaction rates are possible at higher temperatures and pressures with large granules. Superheated steam effectively penetrates the protective passivation layer of alumina, resulting in formation of a pure Al₂O₃ and hydrogen. The report provides a detailed evaluation of the raw fuel material's characteristics, such as the material's dimensions, shape, and composition, which all contribute to the overall conversion rate. The experimental results obtained for different Al granule shapes and sizes showed a strong dependence between granule morphology and reaction rates. We evaluated how reactive different Al fuels influenced reaction kinetic by measuring the amount of H₂ that was produced and keeping an eye on the reaction parameters. We were able to find good model to describe the behavior of available fuels that can be changed to a desired product. Presented results confirmed that aluminium-superheated steam reactions are an effective way at making hydrogen and heat fast enough for seasonal storage use, helping the future carbon-neutral society realization.

2. Introduction

In the framework of tackling climate change and coping with geopolitical issues, fossil fuel restrictions and the transition towards more sustainable alternatives will require a strategically smart use of alternative energy sources. Staying within reach of the Paris agreements on climate change is possible by phasing out fossil fuels, related to over 94% of global CO₂ emissions, and harvesting all needed energy from renewable sources. In combination with society driven changes, a modelled net zero CO₂ emission scenario by 2050 can limit the global temperature increase to 1.5°C by the end of the century. The development of long-term storage of clean energy and the ability to transport and distribute this globally will be crucial to bring the milestones into reality. On short term, the global energy sector is expected to achieve an 18% reduction in CO₂ emissions by 2035 by electrification and decarbonisation of electricity. Further deep emission cuts in industry, transport and buildings can be reached by using low-emission fuels, sustainable bio-energy, hydrogen and hydrogen-based fuels, also leading to an 18% drop in CO₂ emissions by 2035. Improved energy efficiency will result in a further 12% decrease in CO₂ emissions by 2035. To achieve the required electrification of the energy market, capacity additions of renewables should triple in comparison to 2022 levels. Additional annual capacity of 1200 GW should be met by 2030, while more than 90% of this expansion should be from renewables by 2027.^{1, 2, 3, 4}

Based on cost-competitiveness and scalability, most of this growth is expected to come from on- and off-shore wind and solar. Price of utility scale solar energy already declined below coal and natural gas generated electricity respectively in 2012 and 2014 for the USA. The market will therefore drive capacity expansion towards renewables. These variable renewables (VRE) are by nature highly unpredictable and prone to short- and longterm fluctuations, resulting in an insecure energy supply. In the coming years, certain countries are already expected to reach a high share of VRE. There will be weeks with electricity surplus and periods with deficits where demand can not be covered by renewables.⁵ Balancing out both phenomena will be crucial to reach the short-term milestones in different climate scenarios, without requiring additional capacity and extensive grid adaptations. Transformation between types of energy and flexible storage over time are crucial, as any surplus of energy when renewables are abundant should be used in times of deficit. Energy storage systems (ESS) are being extensively examined and developed, giving offerings based on type of energy carrier (physical, chemical, electrochemical, thermal), energetic capacity, charge and discharge rate, etc. Hourly and daily fluctuations can be balanced out by use of batteries in combination with smart demand side response, e.g. in industry or by using electric vehicle-to-grid technology. As the share of wind and solar increases, periods of surpluses and deficits will eventually become longer, trespassing daily variations towards weekly and seasonal periods of surplus or deficit.^{6, 7, 8}

Flexibility beyond the hourly range is currently mainly managed by hydropower plants, prone to interannual variations, and legacy thermal power plants, which need to be phased out. Certain low emission fuels, such as green H₂ and ammonia, can add flexibility to a VRE system, but rely on extensive infrastructure, investments in fuel transport, storage, safety and supply assets. Seasonal variability needs to be maintained

by long-term, large capacity storage and is currently mainly provided by storage hydropower, which are limited due to construction costs and geographical/environmental constraints. Other alternatives are mainly in development phase.

This implies that there is room for an ESS with longer storage time combining high capacity, high volumetric energy density and good long-term stability using an abundant, sustainable and environmentally clean fuel. Storing energy in a smartly chosen chemical energy carrier, “X”, can deliver all those requirements. Long-term storage and efficient transport of the fuel are within reach if “X” has a high specific energy, i.e. aluminium, is chemically stable and is energy-dense. In a Power-to-“X” cycle, excess renewable resources in periods of surplus energy are used to produce or recycle this energy carrier of choice.

Aluminium is in this sense one of the chemical carriers that is interesting for long-term chemical storage (Power-to-Alu). It has intrinsically high specific energy (8.7 kWh/kg)⁹, good volumetric energy density (23.5 MWh/m³), a controlled oxidation rate for safety and chemical stability, is highly abundant and, due to developments to replace the Hall-Héroult process with carbon-free aluminium smelting processes, also sustainably recyclable. All of this gives great potential towards Power-to-X energy storage and X-to-Energy energy supply, where “X” is Al. Using a light metal such as aluminium, H₂ can be generated via a highly exothermic reaction, releasing both thermal energy and H₂ in-situ whenever needed. In-situ generation of H₂, in combination with H₂ fuel cells for electricity generation is interesting, as it avoids the need for storage and transport of H₂, eliminating major safety issues related to compressed H₂. The projected experimental volumetric energy density of aluminium at an efficiency of 67% or higher (> 15 MWh/m³) outperforms the one of batteries, H₂, biomass or compressed methane by a factor of 80, 7, 7 and 2 respectively. It even outperforms conventional fossil fuels.¹⁰

The basic oxidation behaviour of aluminium has previously been studied and is heavily dependent on the spontaneous formation of a thin passivation layer in the nanoscale range in air.^{11,12} Al₂O₃ is created on the surface of the aluminium and protects the rest of the material from oxidation in ambient conditions, giving rise to its high long-term stability. Breaking through this passivation layer beyond the nanoscale and extracting all possible energy from the exothermic oxidation reaction is decisive for seasonal energy storage. This can be performed by working in basic conditions, which leads to following reactions:^{13, 14}

The reaction pathway in the presented work shows that making use of superheated steam forms another viable option to break through the passivation layer:

Beneficial to this higher temperature route is the increased efficiency in the Power-to-Al cycle, where all available surplus renewable energy can be directly used during the CO₂ free inert anode reduction from Al₂O₃ to Al-fuel¹⁵ without need for refinement steps to calcinate the hydroxides, which are formed in the low temperature reaction route. This boosts efficiency for the Power-to-Al and increases competitiveness with other EES or energy carriers. This route additionally avoids tapping issues of the aluminium and its reaction products from the reaction medium in case of interacting aluminium under basic conditions. In addition to extracting heat, hydrogen is generated and can be used in fuel cells to produce electricity.¹⁶

The mechanism of how aluminium interacts with water at high temperatures was studied by Nomura¹⁷ in 1960. It was found that grain boundary corrosion for aluminium in high temperature water differs from traditional grain boundary corrosion. He pointed out that grain boundary diffusion of hydrogen atoms, over-voltage of hydrogen produced from the reaction between Al and water and Al₂O₃ surface film properties could influence the reaction speed. By using three different aluminium purities he showed that the pure one presents the largest potential difference and thus the strongest motive force for corrosion. Furthermore, he pointed out that pure Al samples disclose uniform surface corrosion, whereas in contrary, aluminium with impurities in the structure showed high corrosion on grain boundaries. In pure water and by using high-purity aluminium, corrosion speed is mainly determined by grain boundary diffusion of hydrogen atoms. Alloy elements in non-pure aluminium affect the protectiveness of the surface thin film and that way also the overall corrosion. The structure of the formed film had a double-layer structure and the limiting thickness is related to the temperature used. Compact barrier-type oxide forms in contact with the metal and an outer layer of more permeable oxide develops.¹⁸ After reaching limiting thickness, destructive forces are needed to continue the oxidation till the end and to get the most of hydrogen and heat out of the material.¹⁹

A third option to break through the passivation layer could be achieved by refreshing the active surface employing a working temperature above the melting temperature of aluminium. In this case, there are serious implications due to the high reactivity of molten Aluminium with many possible reactor materials.

In the presented work, we study conditions that allow reactants to break through the barrier layer and reach full conversion of the fuel. We examined reaction parameters in terms of temperature and pressure for the steam-assisted oxidation of various Al fuel materials. Raw fuel material characteristics, such as the material's dimensions, shape, and composition, all contribute to the overall conversion rate. The reactivity of different Al fuels was examined by H₂ volume generation evaluation and monitoring of reaction parameters, while chemical and morphological changes of reactants (aluminium) and products (alumina) were studied. We used experimental data to construct a mathematical model, which we further verified at the end. Verification refers to the degree to which the model is performing following the initial modelling assumptions. Fine-tuning the process leads to an economically and practically viable route to seasonal energy storage.

3. Materials and methods

3.1 Materials used

We have performed over 80 experiments using Al materials with different composition, shapes and/or granulate sizes. Fine grained Aluminium STANDART PC 20 flakes (AL-PC20) were purchased from Eckart – Hartenstein. They are produced as an Al containing pigment and were used as a material with the highest purity, lowest particles size and largest surface area. Most of our test were performed using generic aluminium foil (Al-Foil) with a foil thickness of approximately 20 μm as a material with similar edge-to-edge dimensions as the AL-PC20 powder, but with improved handling and safety properties. Fine Aluminium Shot Granal (0.3–1 mm) (Eisenwerk Würth Bad Friedrichshall, Germany) – abbreviated as Al-10Si – was used as a medium sized alloy granulate containing a fraction of Si. For studying different shapes and granulate size, round and cut wire granules of different sizes (0.6, 0.8, 1.0 and 1.2 mm) were purchased from Kuchichel. Furthermore, cut wire granules ($\varnothing = 1.0$ mm) purchased from Krampe Harex (DE)/Carlo Bernasconi AG (CH), together with Al-Deco and Al-Rounded were also used in our experiments (Figure 1).

FIGURE 1: PHOTO OF SOME MATERIALS USED IN EXPERIMENTAL WORK.

3.1.1 Surface area comparison and porosity evaluation

An estimation of the surface area per g of material was made based on the shape and measured dimensions in microscopy and SEM images for all respective aluminium fuels. Below overview in

Table 1 was made under assumption of zero porosity, ideally flat surfaces and no variation in shape between individual particles. Variations, irregularities and imperfections in the fuel surface can be seen in enlargements in Figure 4 to Figure 13.

TABLE 1: ROUGH ESTIMATION OF SURFACE AREA PER G OF SAMPLE.

Al-Fuel	Shape	Diameter (mm)	Height (mm)	Thickness (μm)	Surface area per gram (cm ²)	Maximum obtained conversion (H ₂)
Al-Merck	Cylindrical - Flattened granule	8,95	2,80	NA()	4,3	NA()
Al-CutWire0.6	Cylindrical - Cut wire	0,60	0,50	NA()	39,5	89,6%
Al-CutWire0.8	Cylindrical - Cut wire	0,79	0,78	NA()	28,3	86,2%
Al-CutWire1.0	Cylindrical - Cut wire	0,93	1,00	NA()	23,3	17,3%
Al-CutWire1.2	Cylindrical - Cut wire	1,10	1,12	NA()	20,0	14,5%
Al-Krampe	Cylindrical - Cut wire	1,13	1,01	NA()	20,3	75,6%
Al-Spajic1.6	Cylindrical - Cut wire	1,50	1,43	NA()	15,0	21,4%
Al-PC20	Flakes	0,05	0,0006	NA()	12595,3	10,5%
Al-Foil	Foil	NA()	NA()	15,57	474,0	100,0%
Al-Deco	Irregular - Molten droplet	1,68	NA()	NA()	13,2	93,8%
Al-Rounded0.6	Spherical	0,61	NA()	NA()	36,1	82,3%
Al-Rounded0.8	Spherical	0,93	NA()	NA()	23,8	NA()
Al-Rounded1.0	Spherical	1,13	NA()	NA()	19,6	10,6%
Al-Rounded1.2	Spherical	1,41	NA()	NA()	15,7	NA()
Al-10Si	Spherical - Irregular	1,07	NA()	NA()	20,8	0,7%

FIGURE 2: MICROSCOPY AL-CUTWIRE (LEFT TO RIGHT 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2 MM).

FIGURE 3: SEM AL-CUTWIRE (0.6 AND 1.2 MM).

FIGURE 4: SEM IMAGE OF 1 MM (LEFT) AND 0,8 MM (RIGHT) CUT WIRE GRANULE.

FIGURE 5: MICROSCOPY AL-ROUNDED (LEFT TO RIGHT 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2 MM).

FIGURE 6: SEM AL-ROUNDED (0.6 AND 1.2 MM).

FIGURE 7: MICROSCOPY AL-FUELS (LEFT TO RIGHT AL-10Si - AL-SPAJIC1.6 - AL-DECO - AL-KRAMPE).

FIGURE 8: SEM AL-10Si.

FIGURE 9: SEM AL-SPAJIC1.6.

FIGURE 10: SEM AL-DECO.

FIGURE 11: SEM AL-KRAMPE.

FIGURE 12: MICROSCOPY AL-FUELS (AL-FOIL - AL-MERCK).

FIGURE 13: SEM AL-FOIL (SIDE 1 AND SIDE 2 OF FOIL).

3.1.2 Granules porosity

According to the SEM images above, we anticipated some porosity in the fuel used, but we were wrong. We conducted a pore evaluation on untreated Al-CutWire and Al-Rounded using helium pycnometry. The results show that there is not much porosity trapped, as the measured density is around the expected 2.7 g/cm^3 (Table 2).

TABLE 2: PORE EVALUATION OF ALUMINIUM SAMPLE BEFORE REACTION.

Sample	Volume (cm^3)	Density (g/cm^3)	Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
Al-CutWire 0.6 mm	29.466	2.6913	20
Al-Rounded 0.6mm	30.787	2.6959	20

3.1.3 Impurities SEM/EDS

Various elements are added to aluminium with the purpose to tune the alloy structure and other properties. When using aluminium as a sustainable material, recycling is crucial. A low amount of impurities is expected to result in a more predictable and easier to control circular process of on 1 side producing the aluminium in the smelting process and on the other hand providing energy in the Al-to-Energy process. Due to the circular nature of the storage cycle, impurities could accumulate in aluminium and hinder the complete process recycling process. In our experimental work, different materials accessible on the market were used for testing reaction properties and reaction kinetics. In Table 3 results of quantitative analysis by SEM/EDS are presented. Chemical composition and distribution of possible alloying elements in the fuel materials were analysed by SEM and EDS and presented on the following pages. Analysis was done on samples embedded in epoxy. All EDS results were taken on scans at 5000x magnification. Commonly found alloy elements were Si, Fe, Mg, Mn, C, and Ca. The first 4 elements are present in many alloys (1xxx to 9xxxx) and partly inherent to

the composition of e.g. the bauxite ore which is used to produce metallic aluminium. Carbon can be dissolved into the cryolite melt during the Hall-Héroult process (which should not be an issue for the proposed CO₂ free smelting process), while Ca can be added to improve corrosion resistance to several Al-alloys.

TABLE 3: QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS ON DIFFERENT FUEL MATERIALS BY ENERGY DISPERSIVE SPECTROSCOPY (EDS).

Al-Fuel source	Al	O	Si	C	Mg	Fe	Mn	Ca	Conductive layer	Comment
Al-10Si	84,8	2,9	12,0		0,3				C	Center of granule
Al-CutWire1.2	81,1	4,5	1,4	12,2	0,3	0,4		0,1	Au	Edge of granule
Al-CutWire1.2	82,8	4,3	1,1	11,3	0,3	0,2			Au	Center of granule
Al-Deco	50,4	10,2	1,6	35,5	0,1	1,1		1,1	Au	Center of granule
Al-Deco	55,1	8,0	0,3	34,7	0,1	0,2	0,5	1,2	Au	Center of granule
Al-Deco	68,0	7,1	0,4	22,9			0,9	0,9	Au	Edge of granule
Al-Foil	78,8	16,1	1,2			3,9			C	Over width of foil
Al-Foil	77,8	19,2	1,6			1,4			C	Over width of foil
Al-Foil	84,1	9,7	1,4			4,8			C	Over width of foil
Al-Krampe	82,8	3,7	0,9	12,3	0,3				Au	Center of granule
Al-Krampe	79,6	4,2	1,0	14,6	0,3	0,3			Au	Edge of granule
Al-Merck	91,8	6,0	2,1						C	Edge of granule
Al-Rounded	71,3	6,1	2,9	19,2	0,3	0,1		0,1	Au	Center of granule
Al-Rounded	75,9	5,2	1,3	16,8	0,3	0,3		0,2	Au	Edge of granule
Al-Spajic1.6	37,6	9,5	0,4	49,7	0,4	0,1		2,4	Au	Center of granule
Al-Spajic1.6	71,9	6,5	2,5	18,5	0,3	0,2		0,1	Au	Center of granule
Al-Spajic1.6	50,5	9,0	0,4	38,2	0,4	0,1		1,4	Au	Center of granule

Based on the elemental compositions in Table 3, we can divide the raw fuels in 4 groups:

3.1.3.1 High-Si alloy

- Al-10Si

FIGURE 14: EDS SPECTRUM FOR AL-10Si (LEFT) AND EDS TRUMAP (RIGHT).

Besides Si, there was detection of small amounts of Mg. All elements were homogeneously distributed within the scanned area as seen in Figure 14

3.1.3.2 High-C alloy:

- Al-Deco

FIGURE 15: EDS SPECTRUM FOR AL-DECO (LEFT) AND EDS TRUMAP (RIGHT).

For Al-Deco, C-rich and Ca-rich components (likely as CaO) are present as agglomerates inside the fuel. Other traces are homogeneously distributed, as seen in Figure 15

- Al-Spajič1.6

FIGURE 16: EDS SPECTRUM FOR AL-SPAJIČ1.6 (LEFT) AND EDS TRUMAP (RIGHT).

Al-Spajič1.6 results in a similar elemental distribution as Al-Deco, with clear agglomerations of C-rich components. Other elements, also Ca are more homogeneously distributed (Figure 16).

3.1.3.3 Medium-C alloy

- Al-CutWire

FIGURE 17: EDS SPECTRUM FOR AL-CUTWIRE1.2 (LEFT) AND EDS TRUMAP (RIGHT).

For Al-CutWire1.2, all detected elements are relatively well distributed over the cross section of the granule. Fe shows some smaller agglomerates where the concentration is higher (Figure 17).

- Al-Krampe

FIGURE 18: EDS SPECTRUM FOR AL-KRAMPE (LEFT) AND EDS TRUMAP (RIGHT).

Good distribution of all alloy elements is seen for Al-Krampe in Figure 18.

- Al-Rounded

FIGURE 19: EDS SPECTRUM FOR AL-ROUNDED1.2 (LEFT) AND EDS TRUMAP (RIGHT).

For Al-Rounded1.2 we can observe higher concentration of Si and C inside the polishing marks and on a few of the larger agglomerates on the surface. As previously stated, the sandpaper used for polishing is made out of SiC, which could result in contamination of the sample surface. On the other hand visible marks were seen before for some of the other fuels examined, but in those cases didn't result in higher presence of Si and C. Since sample preparation was identical for all samples, it makes presence of Si and C purely due to contamination more unlikely. In that case, inhomogeneous distribution of Si and C is observed for Al-Rounded1.2. Regions with increased concentration of C without Si are also observed, while some smaller Fe-Rich agglomerates are present as well in Figure 19.

3.1.3.4 Low-C alloy

- Al-foil

FIGURE 20: EDS SPECTRUM FOR AL-FOIL (LEFT) AND EDS TRUMAP (RIGHT).

Measuring over a cross section of the 15 μm thick foil embedded in epoxy shows presence of Si and Fe in Figure 20. Si was present as a few smaller agglomerates, while C-rich areas seem to correlate with the darker shades of the underlying secondary electron image. Fe was homogeneously distributed over the foil.

- Al-Merck

FIGURE 21: EDS SPECTRUM FOR AL-MERCK (LEFT) AND EDS TRUMAP (RIGHT).

Si rich agglomerates are seen. C is homogeneously distributed and no detection of traces of other possible alloy elements for this fuel (Figure 21).

3.2 Reaction setup

An in-house built lab scale batch reactor with continuous steam production was used for the study of the oxidation behaviour of aluminium. Reaction conditions and material characteristics have an effect on its reactivity and conversion. Pressure and temperature inside the reactor was examined for different Al-fuel types, with different compositions, shapes and/or granulate sizes. The reaction is in-situ monitored by the evolution of hydrogen gas and afterwards evaluated by changes in mass, morphology and chemical characterisation of the Al-fuel and reaction products to enable insight in the reaction kinetics.

FIGURE 22: P&ID DIAGRAM BATCH REACTOR.

VACUUM PUMP (A) - 3-WAY VALVE (B) - N₂ (C) - WADOSE FLUSYS METERING PUMP (D) - STEAM BOILER (E) - ALUMINIUM REACTOR CHAMBER (F) - FURNACE (G) - THERMOCOUPLE READING (H) - WATER COOLING (I) - EXHAUST POINT (J) - PRESSURE GAUGE (K) – DRASTAR BACKPRESSURE REGULATOR 1-50 BAR (L).

A batch reactor with continuous superheated steam flux (Figure 22) was built around a Bosio EUP-D 20/1200 muffle furnace (G) (Celje, Slovenia). Continuous controlled waterflow and steam generation was created

using a Flusys Wadose HP metering pump (D) (Offenbach am Main, Germany). Steam generation was monitored by temperature readings at the end of the exit tube between steam boiler and reaction chamber (H). Proper steam generation implies temperatures above the critical temperature for water at used reaction pressures inside the system. Chosen reaction pressures were controlled using a Drastar 088S-050A-10-H1 (max 50 bar) (L) (Guro-gu, Seoul, South Korea). Pressures were monitored with Ashcroft 68334-27 pressure gauges, both after the reaction chamber and before the backpressure regulator (K) (Stratford, USA). Temperatures inside the reactor chamber were also monitored to examine the progress of the exothermic oxidation reaction. Generated H₂ was collected and evaluated behind a water lock. Connection tubes (1/16"), steam boiler (E) (15cm - 1/2"), aluminium reaction chamber (20 cm – 1"), fittings and valves were stainless steel and purchased at DK-Lok (Juchon-myeon, Gimhae-si, Gyeongsangnam-do, South Korea). Quartz wool was used as a filter for particulate matter at both ends of the reaction chamber.

3.3 Characterization methods

Moderen characterization methods were used for evaluation of initial and product materials.

3.3.1 SEM/EDS

Surface and cross section micrographs, together with local chemical analysis was determined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) at an accelerating voltage of 10kV, using an FE-SEM Zeiss SUPRA 35 VP instrument (Oberkochen, Germany), equipped with an Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) Solid State Detector (SDD) (Oxford Instruments, High Wycombe, UK).

3.3.2 XRD

The crystal phases present in the reaction products were identified by X-Ray diffraction using a PANalytical X'Pert PRO MPD X-Ray Powder Diffractometer (Malvern Panalytical, Malvern, United Kingdom). Diffractograms were processed using Malvern's XPert HighScore Plus software suite.

3.3.3 XPS

The chemical analysis was performed on the reaction products, focusing on the conversion degree of each studied reaction. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was performed with the Versaprobe 3 AD (Phi, Chanhassen, US) using a monochromatic Al-K α_1 X-ray source. For each measurement, spectra were recorded using a 200 μm spot size (43.2 W, 45.0°, 224 eV pass energy), surface mappings are presented for a 6.6 μm spot size (0.8 W, 45.0°). Measurement data were analysed with PHI Multipak software.

3.3.1 Particle size

Particle size of reaction products was analysed using a Microtrac S 3500 (Microtrac, Osaka, Japan) Laser Particle Size Analyzer equipped with tri-laser technology.

Particle sizes and surface area of aluminium fuel materials were estimated based on optical microscopy and SEM analysis.

3.3.2 TEM

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) and Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (STEM) were carried out on a JEOL ARM 200 CF microscope (Jeol, Tokyo, Japan) operated at 80 kV. Chemical mappings were taken using a SDD Jeol Centurio Energy-Dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectrometer.

3.3.3 Operando Raman

Raman analysis of reaction products was performed using a confocal Raman setup combined with AFM (WiTec Alpha 300RA, Ulm, Germany) using a 532 nm Nd:YAG green laser in combination with large numerical aperture objectives, Zeiss 50x 0,8N.A. and 100x 0.9N.A. (Jena, Germany).

Sub-micron level analysis of surface profiles was performed with AFM in AC tapping mode (force modulation) using reflex coated AFM tips (2,8 N/m, 75 kHz).

3.3.4 Pore size

Nitrogen physisorption analysis was determined from the adsorption and desorption isotherms of N₂ at -196 °C using a Micromeritics TriStar II 3020 instrument. Prior to characterization, the samples were degassed under N₂ stream (purity 6.0) using a programmed bilevel heating, with the first heating stage at 90°C for 60 min, followed by the second heating stage at 150°C for 240 min. The heating rate was set to 10°C min⁻¹ for both heating stages. The specific surface area of the samples was calculated by applying the BET theory to the nitrogen adsorption data within the 0.06–0.30 P/P₀ range. The density (ρ_P) of granules Al-cut wire (0.6 mm) and Al-rounded (0.6 mm) (an average of 10 consecutive measurements) were evaluated using a fully automated, highly precision helium pycnometry (Ultracyc 5000 by Anton Paar). To prevent the influence of moisture and impurities on the measurements, the Al granules were thoroughly dried and purged with nitrogen.

4. Aluminium steam reaction kinetic

It is well known that the surface of aluminium material is covered by spontaneously formed and thermally assisted thin films. Films form a “passivation” layer according to the Cabrera Mott²⁰ model in a first stage and in second phase evolve further by diffusion. In the first stage, the movement of ions through the oxide film is driven by an electric field that is generated within the film itself. The presence of an electric field is caused by the movement of electrons between the Fermi level of the parent metal and the acceptor levels of chemisorbed oxygen at the oxide surface through a process called electron tunnelling. The self-generated electric field decreases the amount of energy required for ions to move through the oxide film. Due to the exponential drop in tunnelling current, the oxidation process effectively stops after the passivation oxide film reaches a certain thickness.²¹ Further oxidation by diffusion of water and hydrogen could be affected by grain boundaries, impurities, defects trapping and temperature.²² In sapphire (single crystals) the diffusion is presumed to take place along dislocations, where in polycrystalline material along grain boundaries. The mechanism of water diffusion in alumina doesn't describe the transport of molecular water, but of ions containing hydrogen, most likely the hydronium ion H_3O^+ . This ion can diffuse by a mechanism associated with a negatively charged oxygen ion next to an AlO defect. Magnesium ions dissolved in pure alumina act as electron acceptors, so the lack of a positive charge when Mg^{2+} substitutes Al^{3+} is compensated by the formation of a mobile electron hole. As the Mg^{2+} ion diameter is much larger than the Al^{3+} ion, its introduction causes much local strain in the alumina structure.²³ Local strain could cause defects in the structure and corresponding additional oxidation. Due to the presence of defects or vacancies at the grain boundaries, pure aluminium easily absorbs and diffuses hydrogen atoms created by the reaction between aluminium and H_2O or OH^- ions. These hydrogen atoms combine to form H_2 gas, leading to the destruction of the crystal structure. The degradation of the crystal structure subsequently impacts the rate at which H_2O or OH^- ions can infiltrate the grain boundaries. The incorporation of hydroxyl groups from water vapor at high temperatures appears to enhance grain-boundary oxygen diffusion in aluminium oxide resulting in faster oxidation. Cold rolling could impact the oxidation rate. The grain boundary corrosion decreases as the boundary structure of aluminium surface was broken by increased cold rolling.¹⁷ Despite the alumina shell on the surface of Al particles preventing further oxidation, it will be dissolved through hydrolysis when the oxide come into contact with water.^{24, 25} Subsequently, a highly exothermic chemical reaction occurs when aluminium reacts with water. The enthalpy of this reaction is significant, at around 420-480 kJ/mol Al.²⁶ In case of aluminium powder and grains <0.2mm this could pose a potential risk, especially in a large storage facility, as the reaction's heat will not have much chance to escape into the surrounding environment, but will remain trapped within the storage area.²⁷ Once the temperature reaches the melting point of the Al powder, it will undergo spontaneous combustion, leading to the ignition of the generated hydrogen and an explosion.

4.1 Effect of temperature

The kinetics controlling the oxidation of pure aluminium exhibit significant variations across different temperature ranges. Starting at room temperature up to approximately 300-350°C, oxidation is most accurately characterized by the inverse logarithmic law. The thickness of the oxide coating increases in accordance with a parabolic law within the temperature range of 350°C to 450°C. At elevated temperatures, approaching the point of melting, more complex kinetics are observed. This leads to greater overall weight increases, surpassing what would typically be predicted based on the growth laws at lower temperatures.²⁸ For micron-sized and larger aluminium particles, the ignition temperature coincides with the melting point of the surface oxide (Al_2O_3) layer at 2327 K.²⁹ After the layer has melted, it combines together to create a cap made of oxide, and as a result, the aluminium core becomes exposed to the surrounding gases for oxidation.

To evaluate the effect of temperature on aluminium-steam reaction kinetics in Figure 23, the results of the volume of hydrogen gas in mL per gram of aluminium are presented as a function of reaction time. The experiment involved rolling around 10 g of aluminium foil in a tube reactor, as shown in Figure 1 and Figure 13. We purged the steam through the reactor after it reached temperatures of 450, 500, and 550°C, respectively and kept the pressure constant at 30 bar.

FIGURE 23: VOLUME OF HYDROGEN PER GRAM OF FUEL AS A FUNCTION OF TIME.

From Figure 23, it is evident that temperature influences the start of the reaction and the hydrogen evolution speed. At 550°C, hydrogen evolution starts after 25 minutes, in contrast to at 450°C, where hydrogen evolution starts after 45 minutes of purging the reactor with pressurized overheated steam. Formation of hydrogen and consequent oxidation of aluminium could be described by simple parabolic law. Excellent agreement regarding parabola shape and oxide weight gain was observed with Beck et al.²⁸ where they pointed out formation of different oxides at temperature between 450 and 575 °C. They observed amorphous and crystalline γ -Al₂O₃ formation in reaction with oxygen at elevated temperatures.

It is worth to point out that all experiments run for 6 hours and conversion efficiency at the end was not 100% (1245 mL/g of aluminium) for all of them for several reasons; i.e uneven size distribution, composition, cold mechanical modification, surface area, as discussed in section below.

When aluminium undergoes a reaction with water, it theoretically generates a substantial amount of heat, of around 4.9 kWh/kg Al, and produces 0.111 kg of H₂ gas as well as around 1.9 kg of aluminium oxide for every kilogram of aluminium used. The precise heat and product composition of aluminium-water depend on the thermodynamic circumstances, specifically the temperature and pressure. When using only 10 g of aluminium, for safety reasons during experiments, evaluating the produced heat can be challenging due to the high emittance of the reactor on the surface and surroundings. Therefore we equipped the reactor with inline thermocouples just before and in the middle of the reaction chamber, allowing us to evaluate local increases in temperature during the oxidation reaction.

FIGURE 24: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF STEAM TEMPERATURE, REACTOR TEMPERATURE, PRESSURE AND EVOLVED HYDROGEN AS A FUNCTION OF REACTION TIME FOR REACTION OF AL FOIL AT 500°C AND 30 BAR.

From Figure 24 it is evident that when starting to purge the reactor with steam at 500°C, we reach the target pressure in a few minutes. Once we reach the working pressure, we observe a slight delay before the first evolution of hydrogen gas becomes visible. We observe a slow release of hydrogen during the start of oxidation, with no detectable increase in reactor temperature. We detect rapid oxidation in the second stage, marked by a high production of hydrogen gas and a significant increase in reactor temperature. A quenching phase occurs when most of the fuel has reacted, causing the reactor temperature to drop towards the predetermined value of 500°C. At the same time, hydrogen production also slows down. Similar was observed for the foil fuel (Figure 25).

FIGURE 25: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF STEAM TEMPERATURE, REACTOR TEMPERATURE, PRESSURE AND EVOLVED HYDROGEN AS A FUNCTION OF REACTION TIME FOR REACTION OF AL FOIL AT 500°C AND 30 BAR.

To test self-sustainability of the reaction, we stop external heating once oxidation reaction is ongoing and allow the reactor to cool down as can be seen in Figure 26, while maintaining a stable reactor pressure of approximately 30 bar. Oxidation rate can be divided into 3 separate stages when evaluating the volume of produced hydrogen per gram of aluminium as a function of time. In a first stage, where the reactor gradually cools down from the set temperature to approximately 400°C, reaction rate is high. We observe a small positive difference between temperature inside the reaction chamber and the steam temperature due to the exothermic character of the ongoing oxidation reaction. The amount of energy released is not high enough to keep the entire system at a stable temperature without additional isolation or miniaturisation of the

reactor system. In a second phase the temperature drops below 400°C and the reaction rate clearly decreases. Since there is less exothermic energy being released there is hardly any difference between temperature in the reaction chamber and temperature of the steam. In a third phase, once the temperature of the generated steam drops below 330°C, we observed an unexpected upward trend in the H₂ generation. In this stage it is difficult to have a stable generation of superheated steam, as the temperature inside the steam boiler drops to the critical temperature of water at present pressure level. In the reaction chamber itself though temperatures stay well above the critical temperature due to the exothermicity of the reaction. At this point it seems we are only generating the superheated steam inside the reaction chamber. This change in medium inside the reaction chamber seems to have a positive effect on reaction rate during this stage. Differences in steam characteristics in this temperature range can also account for the increased reaction rate. Reaction slows down once the majority of the fuel is oxidised and superheated steam is no longer being generated inside the reaction chamber. Out of the presented data, we showed that at 30 bar and a high enough starting temperature, we are able to burn all the fuel in the batch reactor without any modifications. In order to achieve self-sustainability in continuous setup, modifications in terms of insulation, size and reactor materials are likely needed.

FIGURE 26: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF STEAM TEMPERATURE, REACTOR TEMPERATURE, PRESSURE AND EVOLVED HYDROGEN AS A FUNCTION OF REACTION TIME IN CASE OF DECREASING THE OUTSIDE REACTOR TEMPERATURE FOR REACTION OF AL FOIL AT 500°C AND 30 BAR.

4.2 Effect of pressure

The reaction between aluminium and steam is influenced not only by temperature but also by pressure. Increasing the pressure generally enhances the rate of reaction between aluminium and water.^{30, 30, 31} Several studies have investigated how varying the pressure affects both the kinetics and the mechanism of this reaction.

The general reaction between aluminium and steam is as follows:

This reaction produces aluminium oxide (Al_2O_3) and hydrogen gas (H_2). The effect of pressure on the reaction between aluminium and water is not straightforward and may depend on the specific conditions. However, one can provide a qualitative explanation based on Le Chatelier's principle. According to this principle, if you increase the pressure of a system at equilibrium, the reaction will shift in the direction that reduces the total number of moles of gas.

In the case of the reaction between aluminium and water, the right side of the equation has 1 mole of solid Al_2O_3 and 3 moles of H_2 gas compared to six moles of H_2O as liquid at the left side. Therefore, increasing the pressure would generally favor the side of the reaction with fewer moles of gas, inhibiting the reaction between aluminium and water.

Under normal conditions, reaction between aluminium and water is not typically a significant safety concern. The protective oxide layer on aluminium's surface usually prevents rapid reactions with water. However, the reaction becomes more relevant under certain conditions, such as a high pressure. Increasing the pressure generally enhances the rate of reaction between aluminium and water.

The reaction efficiency as a function of reaction pressure is shown in Figure 27, Figure 28 and Figure 29. To evaluate the effect of pressure on aluminium-steam reaction, a series of experiments were conducted using the same temperatures as presented in section 4.1. In each experiment, 10 g of aluminium foil was rolled into a tube reactor and purged with steam after reaching temperatures of 450, 500, and 550°C. For each temperature, the experiment was carried out at different pressures: 1, 5, 10, 20 and 30 bars. The results are presented as a volume of generated hydrogen gas in mL per gram of aluminium as a function of reaction time.

Up to 10 bars, there is very little difference between results at different temperatures. However, as the pressure increases, the difference in yield of hydrogen gas also increases. Current data show that full conversion can be achieved for all reactions at 500°C and 30 bar, with some minor differences in reaction rate. Reaction rate is always quick in the first half of the reaction, with 50 % conversion always reached within 80 min. Also, reactions at 30 bar give a good compromise between high reaction rates, full conversion and maintainable conditions for the reactor lifespan. At 30 bar, reactions at 550°C seem to have the highest reaction rates, at least initially, but tend to reach a plateau in the second part of the reaction. The reaction

at 450°C is slower than for both reactions at 500 and 550°C. Even for slower reaction rates at 450 and 550°C, hydrogen yields above 80-90 % can be reached within 6h..

Trends for experiments at 20 bar are similar with hydrogen yields reaching between 40 and 50 %, except for a temperature of 550°C where the yield is lower around 10 %. Using high pressures during the reaction proved to be the most efficient oxidizer, both in terms of rates and yields of hydrogen. High-pressure, high-temperature aluminium–water reactions hold the most promise for hydrogen production at rates high enough to satisfy future domestic energy requirements, particularly towards and decarbonisation of heating demand.

FIGURE 27: VOLUME OF HYDROGEN PRODUCTION GAS IN ML PER GRAM OF ALUMINIUM AT A TEMPERATURE OF 450°C AND DIFFERENT PRESSURES.

FIGURE 28: VOLUME OF HYDROGEN PRODUCTION GAS IN ML PER GRAM OF ALUMINIUM AT A TEMPERATURE OF 500°C AND DIFFERENT PRESSURES.

FIGURE 29: VOLUME OF HYDROGEN PRODUCTION GAS IN ML PER GRAM OF ALUMINIUM AT A TEMPERATURE OF 550°C AND DIFFERENT PRESSURES.

4.3 Effect of the granule size / surface area

Fine aluminium powder has been widely used in propulsion processes because of their elevated oxidation energy and rapid oxidation rates.³² Particles at nanoscales have numerous thermo-physical characteristics that differ from those observed at microscales. Particle size plays a significant role in determining the characteristics of ignition and combustion.³³ When the size drops beyond a certain point, the melting temperature deviates from the value for larger volumes due to the increase in the ratio of surface area to volume. This change in melting temperature becomes dependent on the size of the object.³⁴ Nevertheless, manufacturers, transport sectors, and recycling factories are increasingly concerned about the safety of storing and transporting aluminium powder. In recent years, we have seen reports of fire and explosion incidents. A devastating Al dust explosion, triggered by water, took place in China in 2014. The explosion originated in the dust collection barrel of a major industrial operation that processes workpieces for polishing automotive wheel hubs.³⁵ The presence of molten aluminum makes accidents even more dangerous.³⁶ The Al - H₂O reaction, which resulted in a significant release of heat and hydrogen, was determined to be the primary cause of the accidents. Although the alumina shell on the surface of Al particles serves as a protective barrier preventing further oxidation, it can be dissolved under specific conditions through hydrolysis when the particles come into contact with water and result in safety issues, which has to be kept in mind for future development of the energy storage technique.^{24, 25}

The original project idea was to use granules of 500–1500 microns in size, that are user-friendly and safe for long-term storage applications. In the experimental work presented in D4.2, a large amount of data is collected on aluminium foil as a fuel, which is only approximately 15 micron thick, but offers a high surface area of around 500 cm² per gram of aluminium. All reactions with foil at a pressure of 30 bar or higher, starting at a temperature of 450°C and higher, enable high conversion efficiency. When using granules, the surface area that is available for interaction with steam is much smaller (Figure 30) per gram of aluminium in contrast to foil. For successful extraction of energy (hydrogen and heat), a lower surface area necessitates higher pressure compared to using aluminium foil as fuel. From Figure 30 it is evident that cut wire granules produced out of wire with a diameter of 1.2 mm offer much slower hydrogen evolution with time in comparison to granules produced out of 0.6 mm wire.

FIGURE 30: VOLUME OF PRODUCED HYDROGEN IN ML PER GRAM OF ALUMINIUM AS A FUNCTION OF TIME FOR DIFFERENT GRANULES DIAMETERS.

There are a variety of reasons for the mentioned behavior. First of all we have the direct effect of the surface area per gram of fuel, but also ratio between surface and bulk material, passivation film thickness or consequences of the manufacturing process for the different fuels – such as elongation of the wire which can result in micronisation of grains or remaining organic material on the wire surface due to machining or composition of starting material. During the evaluation of the starting material, we observed that cutting edges are not uniform, depending on cutting tool sharpness or material hardness. Some samples showed pore-like structures on the cutting edges, while others showed smooth surfaces. It is known that adding various elements improves aluminium hardness.

4.4 Repeatability

Reactions of aluminium foil at 500°C and 30 bar were tested more closely for repeatability. As can be seen from the Figure 31 good repeatability is achieved, with some slight differences in the reaction rate. Under these conditions, not only good repeatability but also complete conversion and the highest yield of hydrogen

is achieved. Typically, the reaction rate is fast in the first half of the reaction, with 50% conversion always achieved within 80 minutes. In the second half of the reaction, there are some variations between repeated reactions, possibly due to differences in the composition of the fuel, differences in sampling or the condition of the reactor tubes.

FIGURE 31: REPEATABILITY OF REACTION OF ALUMINIUM FOIL AT THE SAME CONDITIONS.

5. Alumina composition and recycling feasibility

5.1 Surface morphology of products

FIGURE 32: SEM IMAGES OF FOILS SURFACE AFTER INTERACTION WITH STEAM AT 500°C FOR 6 HOURS.

When we use a high temperature (500°C) for the interaction of aluminium foil with steam for six hours (Figure 32), we can observe a slight change on the surface of the aluminium foil. As discussed above, at low pressure, oxide growth stopped at limiting thickness. We will discuss the thickness and composition in the XPS results section. Higher pressure (20 bar) reveals more irregularities on the surface due to the larger volume of alumina compared to aluminium. Stress is present on the surface, and cracks appear with time. Those cracks and pores serve as a highway for water to penetrate the unreacted surface and cause the oxide to grow. Above 20 bars, the decomposition is so severe that oxidation takes place throughout the entire volume, and almost 100 percent conversion efficiency is easily achievable for foil fuel. We observe similar behaviour at higher working pressure.

A more detailed insight in oxidation process is evident from cross-sectional morphologies out of SEM images (Figure 33), where only partial surface oxidation (brighter areas) is visible when using 1 bar working pressure, more damaged bulk when using 10 bar, and severely damaged when using 20 bar working pressure.

FIGURE 33: CROSS-CUT SEM IMAGES OF FOIL AFTER REACTION AT 500°C USING 1, 10 AND 20 BARS WORKING PRESSURE.

FIGURE 34: SEM IMAGES OF STRUCTURALLY MORE INTACT (LEFT) AND STRUCTURALLY MORE DEGRADED (RIGHT) AREAS OF THE FOIL AFTER REACTION AT HIGH PRESSURE.

When the oxidation speed varies in areas with large grains, grain orientations, and impurity inclusions, the resulting alumina material is not uniform even after high conversion. When analysing the alumina product after a complete reaction, some areas at different pressures remain merged together, evidently less cracked at lower pressure and more porous at higher working pressure (Figure 34). All the remaining powder material

forms from the agglomeration of small oxide particles into larger particles. Agglomerates can be easily pulverised, requiring no additional mechanical treatment before recycling. We will discuss the dependence of particle size on temperature in the particle size section.

FIGURE 35: SEM HIGH MAGNIFICATION IMAGES OF DIFFERENT GRANULES AFTER HIGH CONVERSION REACTIONS.

Similar to the fine alumina powder final product made out of foil at 30 bar or more, we can observe fine powder product after reaction at high pressure for different granules. We achieved high conversion for granules when we used working pressure above 45 bars.

5.2 Alumina article size distribution

Particle sizes by number all fall within the same range, the standard deviation is possibly related to unreacted part of the fuel when the reaction is stopped before 100% conversion. These larger agglomerates can act as a physical filter between the reactor and the rest of the setup and can help to keep the system operating with

less risk of blockage or pressure loss. Having some larger agglomerates present can also contribute to good flow and contact between steam and Al-fuel, keeping the reaction rate high. In TEM analysis for sample Al-Foil – 500°C - 30 bar, we can see individual single phase crystallites with sizes in the 10s of nanometer range. These crystallites form larger agglomerates, which we can see in presented SEM images.

TABLE 4: PARTICLE SIZES OF REACTION PRODUCT AFTER HIGH CONVERSION REACTIONS.

Experiment	Particle diameter AVG,VOL (μm)	Particle diameter AVG,NUM (μm)	Standard deviation (μm)	Conversion (H_2) (%)
Al-Foil – 350°C-40 bar (2023-08-29)	55,11	7,6	4,36	100,0%
Al-Foil – 450°C-30 bar (2023-08-10)	37,78	8,49	17,07	89,6%
Al-Foil – 500°C-30 bar (2023-07-24)	27,91	6,28	3,1	100,0%
Al-Foil – 550°C-30 bar (2023-08-18)	64,08	7,73	36,05	81,0%
Al-DECO – 550°C-40 bar (2023-09-14)	55,47	8,41	36,81	93,8%

Particle sizes are presented in detail in Figure 36 showing the influence of temperature on particle size for reaction on Al-foil at 30 bar. The reaction at 500°C and 30 bar resulted in the most narrow particle size distribution with a D90 value of approximately 13 μm . Reactions at 450 and 550°C respectively result in D90 values of 18 and 16 μm . Particle sizes (and active surface area of the material) have been related to presence of different Al_2O_3 phases, as mentioned in BET measurements and XRD results.

FIGURE 36: PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTIONS FOR AL-FOIL REACTED AT 30 BAR (T = 450-500-550°C).

5.3 Alumina pores evaluation

The nitrogen gas adsorption–desorption isotherms were made for aluminium foil after reaction at 500°C and 30 bar. The features of the isotherms mostly correspond to type II according to the IUPAC classification³⁷, which refers to materials without mesoscale porosity. From Figure 37 it can be seen that up to 0.01 p/p_0 , there is an adsorption of N_2 of approximately 4-5 cm^3/g , corresponding to the micropores, which constitute the majority of the total surface area, which is 23 m^2/g . Mesoporosity is practically absent, as indicated by the relatively flat portion of the isotherm between 0.1 and 0.3 p/p_0 . The presence of macropores is evident from the increased amount of N_2 adsorbed at 0.8-0.9 p/p_0 , a finding supported by SEM analysis. The curve does not display any hysteresis effects, indicating the absence of capillary condensation and suggesting a lack of mesopores. There is no chemosuppression, as the amounts of nitrogen adsorbed and desorbed match.

FIGURE 37: N_2 ADSORPTION-DESORPTION ISOTHERMS OF ALUMINIUM FOIL AFTER REACTION.

5.4 Phase composition

The alumina composition and structure can be resolved from XRD analysis. If a sharp peak is observed, it infers a crystalline nature; otherwise, an amorphous nature of the surface is inferred. Beck et al.²⁸ presents years ago, that examination of stripped oxide films showed the simultaneous presence of $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, crystals and amorphous $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, during some period of oxidation at all temperatures between 450 and 575 °C. Similar alumina forms are produced for most of Al-steam reactions in our work if we exclude the experiments at 250°C and high pressure (40 bar) where we observed transformation of aluminium into boehmite (Figure 38). It is worth to mention that boehmite is not favorized for recycling as it needs additional thermal treatment before recycling process can start.

FIGURE 38: XRD DIFFRACTOGRAM FOR INITIAL AL FOIL (LEFT) AND FOIL REACTION PRODUCT AT LOW TEMPERATURE – BOEHMITE (RIGHT).

Crystal structure identified by boehmite diffractogram is confirmed by SEM image (Figure 39).

FIGURE 39: SEM – FORMATION OF CHIPPED MATERIAL WITH DIFFERENT SIZES ON THE SURFACE AFTER REACTION AT 250°C AND 40 BAR (AL-FOIL – 250°C – 40 BAR).

As already discussed, high conversion of aluminium to alumina resulted in fine aluminiumoxide powder. Amorphous or crystalline phase is confirmed by XRD diffractograms of reaction products for high conversion experiments. Full transformation to gamma alumina is evident from Figure 40 (right). It is worth to mention that small amounts of aluminium, resulting in sharp intense peaks in the diffractograms, remain present in the reaction product if reaction did not reach full conversion. Alumina peaks on the contrary result in weaker and broader diffraction peaks (Figure 40 left).

FIGURE 40: XRD DIFFRACTOGRAM SHOWING MAINLY SINGLE PHASE GAMMA Al_2O_3 AS ANNOTATED PEAKS AND SOME UNREACTED AL (AL-FOIL – 550°C – 30 BAR – LEFT // AL-FOIL – 500°C – 30 BAR - RIGHT).

The aluminium oxide form depends strongly on the starting material (e.g., hydrated, thermally oxidized, alkoxide, metal, etc.), the impurities present, and on thermal history. In our case, aluminium at high temperature and in contact with steam results in gamma phase formation (Figure 41 left). Transformation from gamma to alpha is expected to occur at elevated temperatures above 1100°C. Surprisingly, in our experiments transformation happens already at temperatures near 500°C (Figure 41).

FIGURE 41: TRANSFORMATION SEQUENCE FOR VARIOUS TRANSITION ALUMINA (LEFT), MIXTURE (GAMMA AND ALPHA (RIGHT)).³⁸

5.5 TEM

A TEM scan of the sample Al-Foil at 500°C and 30 bar confirmed that the crystallites we were studying had single-phase gamma. All peaks in the diffractogram spanning multiple crystallites could be assigned by gamma-Al₂O₃ or by pure Al.

FIGURE 42: TEM DIFFRACTOGRAM AL-FOIL – 500°C-30 BAR (2023-07-24) – MILLER INDICES FOR GAMMA PHASE ASSIGNMENT IN BLUE.

FIGURE 43: MEASURED AND CALCULATED DIFFRACTION PATTERN OF THE 110 FACE OF GAMMA – Al₂O₃ CRYSTALS.

Diffraction patterns on individual crystallites match with the calculated diffraction pattern for the gamma- Al_2O_3 crystals.

The other experiments leading to high conversion of Al-foil material all show a mix of alfa and gamma- Al_2O_3 , as shown in example diffractograms for one of the experiments performed at 500°C and 30 bar, with annotated peaks for gamma and alfa- Al_2O_3 (Figure 41 right).

5.6 Oxidation initiation by steam – XPS analysis

XPS analysis was performed to see the onset of the oxidation reaction. Al-10Si granules before and after reaction with steam at 500°C and 1 bar showed a clear increase in oxidation near the surface of the granules, as seen in respectively Figure 44 and Figure 45. For the untreated fuel, presence of oxygen near the surface is related to the existence of a passivation layer near the surface. As the atomic ratio between oxygen and aluminium increases from 57/11 for the untreated up to 62/2 for the oxidised sample, it shows that breaking through the passivation layer and initiating oxidation of the underlying fuel is possible through steam assisted oxidation, already at atmospheric pressures.

FIGURE 44: XPS SPECTRA AND MAPPING ON UNTREATED AL – 10Si GRANULES.

FIGURE 45: XPS SPECTRA AND SURFACE MAPPING ON OXIDIZED AL-10SI GRANULES (AL-10SI – 500°C – 1 BAR).

When evaluating - using Al-foil as a fuel - the depth below the surface obtainable for the oxidation reaction with steam at atmospheric pressures, we can see that the majority of the oxidation in these conditions happens in the top 2 μm of the foil, based on binding energies of Al(2p) electrons (Figure 46) and atomic ratios between O and Al (Figure 47).

FIGURE 46: BINDING ENERGY FOR AL(2P) OVER DEPTH BELOW THE SURFACE.

Progressive shifts in binding energy for Al(2p) can be observed when measuring deeper below the surface. In the first cycle, at the surface of the material, a binding energy of 74,2 eV is measured. We can see a gradual shift to binding energies around 72,5 eV for cycles 2, 3 and 4 down to 540 nm below the surface. While the last 2 cycles up to 1080 nm below the surface show a shift towards a binding energy of approximately 72 eV. It has been shown that the binding energy increases with the degree of oxidation, and that Al(2p) electrons for metallic aluminium have a binding energy between 72 and 73 eV, while the binding energy for those electrons in Al₂O₃ increases to values between 74 and 75 eV.³⁹ Based on this, and combined with confirmation from other techniques, it is likely that at the surface Al₂O₃ is present as the only phase, while deeper down - below the passivation layer thickness - we get a mix between metallic aluminium and Al₂O₃ formed during the steam assisted oxidation of aluminium.

FIGURE 47: XPS DEPTH PROFILE AND ATOMIC FRACTIONS FOR AL AND O (AL-FOIL – 500°C-1BAR).

From the atomic ratios we can calculate the fraction of Al that was converted into Al₂O₃ in Figure 48. Since we can see a linear trend between cycles 2 (180 nm below the surface) and cycle 7 (1080 nm below the surface), we can assume some degree of oxidation down to 2 μm below the surface when oxidising Al-Foil with superheated steam at 500°C and atmospheric pressures.

FIGURE 48: OBTAINABLE DEPTH FOR OXIDATION AT ATMOSPHERIC PRESSURES (AL-FOIL – 500°C-1 BAR).

5.7 Limitations and pitfalls

One of the main limitations of the kinetic studies made in task 4.2 was the limited information regarding material composition. The delay in granule production for Tasks 4.1 and 4.2 forced us to use materials with an unspecified elemental composition. We had to rely on market-available materials (granules) from various providers who lacked precise knowledge of the material composition. Furthermore, there was a discrepancy in the composition of the batches collected for the research. The batch's composition varied due to the collection of materials from different wires. Consequently, some of the material was completely oxidised, and some granules remained intact.

5.7.1 Uneven material composition

Figure 49 and Figure 50 shows the solid residues obtained in oxidation experiments with aluminium granules (cut wire 0.6 and 0.8 mm). Aluminium oxidation occurred at a studied temperature of 550°C and pressure of 45 bar in a reaction that lasted for 6 hours. After the experiment, a big fraction of the product was converted into fine powder (right side), but structurally more intact aluminium granules were also still observed (left side). The surface became rough and the entire granule a lot more porous. Conversion degrees of aluminium granules cut wire with size 0.6 and 0.8 mm were between 86 - 89 %, where the reaction seems to reach a plateau near the end of the reaction. The presence of some non-reactive species, impurities, alloys or changing reaction conditions possibly negatively affect reaching a 100% of hydrogen yield.

FIGURE 49: SIEVED REACTION PRODUCT AFTER REACTION AT 550°C, 40 BARS FOR 6 H.

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 50: PICTURE OF SIEVED MATERIALS AFTER EXPOSURE TO STEAM AT 550°C AND 45 BAR. PARTIALLY OXIDISED CUT WIRE GRANULES ARE SHOWN ON LEFT SIDE AND FULLY OXIDISED GRANULES AT THE RIGHT SIDE. A) 0.6 MM, B) 0.8 MM.

SEM/EDS analysis was performed to understand material composition after oxidation reaction (Figure 51). EDS analysis indicates presence of alloy elements near the surface of some of the granules, as presented in Figure 51 for Al-Krampe. For Al-Krampe it seems that the surface is covered by a Mg-rich layer, with more pure Al underneath. This impurity layer possibly adds additional resistance to the onset of the oxidation reaction. Evaluation of reactions performed on Al-foil and granular fuel sources (Al-Deco, Al-CutWire, Al-Rounded, Al-Krampe, Al-Spajic), have consistently shown a longer delay between pressuring and filling the system with steam and the moment where generation of H_2 indicated the start of the oxidation reaction.

Figure 52 shows this difference for 2 reactions having a similar degree of conversion (70-80 %). For the oxidation of Al-Foil there is a delay of approximately 20 min, while this increases to 90 min for Al-Krampe.

FIGURE 51: SEM AND EDS MAPPING RESULTS OF PARTIALLY OXIDISED GRANULES OF KRAMPE MATERIAL (550°C/47 BAR/6H).

FIGURE 52: DELAYED ONSET IN OXIDATION FOR AL-FOIL - 550°C - 30 BAR (TOP) AND AL-KRAMPE - 550°C - 45 BAR (BOTTOM).

5.7.2 Volume increase and reactor blocking

A strong increase in volume between the raw fuel and the material during the reaction can effect the performance of the reactor system. The volume expansion factor can be from 1.1 to 1.6.⁴⁰ This phenomenon was also observed in our experiments, where relatively densely packing the reactor tube with fuel resulted in blockage of the tube during high conversion reaction due to expansion of alumina granules over the whole diameter of the tube as presented in Figure 53.

FIGURE 53: PHOTO OF BLOCKED TUBE AFTER REACTION WITH STEAM.

For better operation of our system, reactor tube was only partly filled in order to prevent reactor tube blocking.

6. Mathematical model

Modeling of the hydrogen evolution rate at the instantaneous Al-foil gas interface is performed using a simplified version of the random pore model^{41, 42} in which we assume a chemical reaction control. The rate equation can be written as:

$$\frac{dV(t)}{V_0 dt} = C \left(1 - \frac{V(t)}{V_0}\right) \left(\frac{C\Psi}{2}t + 1\right),$$

with $V(t)$ denoting amount of released H_2 , C the reaction constant and Ψ accounting for the internal particle pore structure, which gives us the analytical solution:

$$V(t) = V_0 \left(1 - \exp\left(-Ct\left(\frac{C\Psi}{4}t - 1\right)\right)\right). \quad (Eq. 1)$$

We make parameter C related to the Arrhenius equation in which we further assume the dependence of activation energy on the water vapor pressure p

$$C = \alpha \exp\left(-\frac{\beta - \gamma p}{T}\right).$$

Fitting of eq. 1 to the existing experimental data gives the following values of Arrhenius equation:

$$\alpha = 1.764 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ min}^{-1},$$

$$\beta = 4480.03 \text{ K and}$$

$$\gamma = 38.8 \text{ K/bar.}$$

Parameters V_0 and Ψ are determined separately for each individual experimental setup. Figure below shows matching between the fit and experimental data for several examples (Figure 54).

FIGURE 54: GRAPHICAL PRESENTATION OF FITTING.

7. Summary and conclusions

The deliverable report D4.2 describes the reaction features of aluminium and superheated steam at high temperatures. The focus is on determining the optimal reaction kinetics to produce heat (exothermic) and electricity (from the production of H₂ in a fuel cell) for energy storage systems operating in various seasons.

To investigate this process, we developed a comprehensive laboratory setup, including a superheated steam production vessel, nitrogen purging, steam introduction, temperature control, and hydrogen measurement. Our study focused on examining reaction parameters, such as temperature and pressure, for the steam-assisted oxidation of various aluminium fuel materials. The goal was to identify the ideal conditions for breaking through the passivation layer and achieving full fuel conversion.

Other significant factors that influenced the conversion rate included the state of matter, dimensions, shape, and composition of the aluminium fuel. Experimental results demonstrated that superheated steam effectively penetrates the protective passivation layer of aluminium, resulting in pure Al₂O₃ and hydrogen. We assessed the reactivity of different aluminium fuels by evaluating H₂ volume generation and monitoring reaction parameters. Additionally, we studied the chemical and morphological changes in the reactants (aluminium) and products (alumina).

Our findings show that high-pressure and high-temperature aluminium-water steam reactions are efficient in producing hydrogen at sufficient rates for demanding decarbonisation applications. In addition, the use of aluminium as a chemical carrier can serve as a cost-effective sustainable fuel for off-grid applications such as winter heating and electricity demand in buildings, thus contributing to a carbon-neutral future.

The experimental data enabled us to construct and verify a mathematical model that can predict reaction rates at relevant conditions.

List of figures

Figure 1: Photo of some materials used in experimental work.	9
Figure 2: Microscopy Al-CutWire (Left to right 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2 mm).....	11
Figure 3: SEM AL-CUTWIRE (0.6 and 1.2 mm).....	11
Figure 4: SEM image of 1 mm (left) and 0,8 mm (right) cut wire granule.	11
Figure 5: Microscopy AL-Rounded (LEFT TO RIGHT 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2 MM).....	12
Figure 6: SEM AL-Rounded (0.6 AND 1.2 MM).....	12
Figure 7: Microscopy Al-Fuels (Left to right Al-10Si - Al-Spajic1.6 - Al-Deco - Al-Krampe).	13
Figure 8: SEM Al-10Si.	13
Figure 9: SEM Al-Spajic1.6.....	13
Figure 10: SEM Al-Deco.....	14
Figure 11: SEM Al-Krampe.	14
Figure 12: Microscopy Al-Fuels (al-Foil - Al-Merck).	14
Figure 13: SEM Al-Foil (Side 1 and side 2 of foil).....	15
Figure 14: EDS spectrum for Al-10Si (left) and EDS TruMap (right).	16
Figure 15: EDS spectrum for Al-Deco (left) and EDS TruMap (right).....	17
Figure 16: EDS spectrum for Al-Spajic1.6 (left) and EDS TruMap (right).	17
Figure 17: EDS spectrum for Al-CutWire1.2 (left) and EDS TruMap (right).	18
Figure 18: EDS spectrum for Al-Krampe (left) and EDS TruMap (right).	18
Figure 19: EDS spectrum for Al-Rounded1.2 (left) and EDS TruMap (right).	19
Figure 20: EDS spectrum for Al-Foil (left) and EDS TruMap (right).	19
Figure 21: EDS spectrum for Al-Merck (left) and EDS TruMap (right).....	20
Figure 22: P&ID diagram batch reactor.....	21
Figure 23: Volume of hydrogen per gram of fuel as a function of time.....	25
Figure 24: Graphical representation of steam temperature, reactor temperature, pressure and evolved hydrogen as a function of reaction time for reaction of Al foil at 500°C and 30 bar.....	26
Figure 25: Graphical representation of steam temperature, reactor temperature, pressure and evolved hydrogen as a function of reaction time for reaction of Al foil at 500°C and 30 bar.....	27
Figure 26: Graphical representation of steam temperature, reactor temperature, pressure and evolved hydrogen as a function of reaction time in case of decreaseing the outside reactor temperature for reaction of Al foil at 500°C and 30 bar.	28
Figure 27: Volume of hydrogen production gas in mL per gram of aluminium at a temperature of 450°C and different pressures.....	30
Figure 28: Volume of hydrogen production gas in mL per gram of aluminium at a temperature of 500°C and different pressures.....	31
Figure 29: Volume of hydrogen production gas in mL per gram of aluminium at a temperature of 550°C and different pressures.....	31

Figure 30: Volume of produced hydrogen in mL per gram of aluminium as a function of time for different granules diameters..... 33

Figure 31: Repeatability of reaction of aluminium foil at the same conditions..... 34

Figure 32: SEM images of foils surface after interaction with steam at 500°C for 6 hours. 35

Figure 33: Cross-cut SEM images of foil after reaction at 500°C using 1, 10 and 20 bars working pressure... 36

Figure 34: SEM images of structurally more intact (left) and structurally more degraded (right) areas of the foil after reaction at high pressure. 37

Figure 35: SEM high magnification images of different granules after high conversion reactions. 38

Figure 36: particle size distributions for Al-Foil reacted at 30 bar (T = 450-500-550°C). 39

Figure 37: N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms of aluminium foil after reaction. 40

Figure 38: XRD diffractogram for initial Al foil (left) and Foil reaction product at low temperature – Boehmite (right)..... 41

Figure 39: SEM – Formation of chipped material with different sizes on the surface after reaction at 250°C and 40 bar (Al-Foil – 250°C – 40 bar). 41

Figure 40: XRD diffractogram showing mainly single phase gamma Al₂O₃ as annotated peaks and some unreacted Al (Al-Foil – 550°C – 30 bar – left // Al-Foil – 500°C – 30 bar - right)..... 42

Figure 41: Transformation sequence for various transition alumina (left), mixture (gamma and alpha (right)).
38 42

Figure 42: TEM diffractogram Al-Foil – 500°C-30 bar (2023-07-24) – Miller indices for gamma phase assignment in blue. 43

Figure 43: Measured and calculated diffraction pattern of the 110 face of gamma – Al₂O₃ crystals. 43

Figure 44: XPS spectra and mapping on untreated Al – 10Si granules. 44

Figure 45: XPS spectra and surface mapping on oxidized Al-10Si granules (Al-10Si – 500°C – 1 bar). 45

Figure 46: Binding energy for Al(2p) over depth below the surface..... 45

Figure 47: XPS depth profile and atomic fractions for Al and O (Al-Foil – 500°C-1bar)..... 46

Figure 48: Obtainable depth for oxidation at atmospheric pressures (Al-Foil – 500°C-1 bar)..... 47

Figure 49: Sieved reaction product after reaction at 550°C, 40 bars for 6 h. 48

Figure 50: Picture of sieved materials after exposure to steam at 550°C and 45 bar. Partially oxidised cut wire granules are shown on left side and fully oxidised granules at the right side. a) 0.6 mm, b) 0.8 mm. 48

Figure 51: SEM and EDS mapping results of partially oxidised granules of Krampe material (550°C/47 bar/6h).
..... 49

Figure 52: DELAYED ONSET IN OXIDATION FOR AL-FOIL - 550°C - 30 BAR (top) AND AL-KRAMPE - 550°C - 45 BAR (bottom)..... 50

Figure 53: Photo of blocked tube after reaction with steam..... 51

Figure 54: Graphical presentation of fitting..... 53

FIGURE 55: MEDIUM CONVERSION (20-80% H₂ GENERATION) - AL-CUTWIRE..... 63

FIGURE 56: MEDIUM CONVERSION (20-80% H₂ GENERATION) - AL-FOIL..... 64

FIGURE 57: MEDIUM CONVERSION (20-80% H₂ GENERATION) - AL-KRAMPE..... 65

FIGURE 58: MEDIUM CONVERSION (20-80% H₂ GENERATION) - AL-SPAJIC1.6..... 66
FIGURE 59: HIGH CONVERSION (80+% H₂ GENERATION) - AL CUTWIRE 67
FIGURE 60: HIGH CONVERSION (80+% H₂ GENERATION) - AL-DECO..... 67
FIGURE 61: HIGH CONVERSION (80+% H₂ GENERATION) - AL-FOIL. 68
FIGURE 62: HIGH CONVERSION (80+% H₂ GENERATION) - AL-ROUNDED. 69
FIGURE 63: HIGH CONVERSION (80+% H₂ GENERATION) - AL-FOIL - REPEATABILITY OF EXPERIMENTS. 70

List of tables

Table 1: Rough estimation of surface area per g of sample.	10
Table 2: Pore evaluation of aluminium sample before reaction.....	15
Table 3: Quantitative analysis on different fuel materials by Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS).....	16
Table 4: Particle sizes of reaction product after high conversion reactions.	39
Table 5: Experiments - low conversion (0-20% H ₂ generation).....	62
Table 6: Experiments - Medium conversion (20-80% H ₂ generation)	63

8. References

- (1) Byers, E.; Krey, V.; Kriegler, E.; Riahi, K.; Schaeffer, R.; Kikstra, J.; Lamboll, R.; Nicholls, Z.; Sandstad, M.; Smith, C.; van der Wijst, K.; Al -Khourdajie, A.; Lecocq, F.; Portugal-Pereira, J.; Saheb, Y.; Stromman, A.; Winkler, H.; Auer, C.; Brutschin, E.; Gidden, M.; Hackstock, P.; Harmsen, M.; Huppmann, D.; Kolp, P.; Lepault, C.; Lewis, J.; Marangoni, G.; Müller-Casseres, E.; Skeie, R.; Werning, M.; Calvin, K.; Forster, P.; Guivarch, C.; Hasegawa, T.; Meinshausen, M.; Peters, G.; Rogelj, J.; Samset, B.; Steinberger, J.; Tavoni, M.; van Vuuren, D. AR6 Scenarios Database, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7197970>.
- (2) Summary for Policymakers. In *Global Warming of 1.5°C: IPCC Special Report on Impacts of Global Warming of 1.5°C above Pre-industrial Levels in Context of Strengthening Response to Climate Change, Sustainable Development, and Efforts to Eradicate Poverty*; Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), Ed.; Cambridge University Press: Cambridge, 2022; pp 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157940.001>.
- (3) Summary for Policymakers. In *Climate Change 2022 – Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability: Working Group II Contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*; Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), Ed.; Cambridge University Press: Cambridge, 2023; pp 3–34. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009325844.001>.
- (4) Summary for Policymakers. In *Climate Change 2021 – The Physical Science Basis: Working Group I Contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*; Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), Ed.; Cambridge University Press: Cambridge, 2023; pp 3–32. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157896.001>.
- (5) Vaziri Rad, M. A.; Kasaeian, A.; Niu, X.; Zhang, K.; Mahian, O. Excess Electricity Problem in Off-Grid Hybrid Renewable Energy Systems: A Comprehensive Review from Challenges to Prevalent Solutions. *Renew. Energy* **2023**, *212*, 538–560. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2023.05.073>.
- (6) Sayed, E. T.; Olabi, A. G.; Alami, A. H.; Radwan, A.; Mdallal, A.; Rezk, A.; Abdelkareem, M. A. Renewable Energy and Energy Storage Systems. *Energies* **2023**, *16* (3), 1415. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16031415>.
- (7) Mitali, J.; Dhinakaran, S.; Mohamad, A. A. Energy Storage Systems: A Review. *Energy Storage Sav.* **2022**, *1* (3), 166–216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enss.2022.07.002>.
- (8) *Critical review of energy storage systems - ScienceDirect*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544220320946?via%3Dihub> (accessed 2024-06-08).
- (9) Haller, M. Y.; Carbonell, D.; Dudita, M.; Zenhäusern, D.; Häberle, A. Seasonal Energy Storage in Aluminium for 100 Percent Solar Heat and Electricity Supply. *Energy Convers. Manag. X* **2020**, *5*, 100017. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecmx.2019.100017>.
- (10) Trowell, K. A.; Goroshin, S.; Frost, D. L.; Bergthorson, J. M. Aluminum and Its Role as a Recyclable, Sustainable Carrier of Renewable Energy. *Appl. Energy* **2020**, *275*, 115112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.115112>.
- (11) Gorobez, J.; Maack, B.; Nilus, N. Growth of Self-Passivating Oxide Layers on Aluminum—Pressure and Temperature Dependence. *Phys. Status Solidi B* **2021**, *258* (5), 2000559. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pssb.202000559>.
- (12) Cai, N.; Zhou, G.; Müller, K.; Starr, D. E. Temperature and Pressure Dependent Mott Potentials and Their Influence on Self-Limiting Oxide Film Growth. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2012**, *101* (17), 171605. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4764552>.
- (13) Teichert, M.; Haller, M. Y.; Sick, F. Aluminium Redox Cycle in Comparison to Pressurized Hydrogen for the Energy Supply of Multi-Family Houses. *Appl. Energy Combust. Sci.* **2023**, *13*, 100098. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaecs.2022.100098>.

- (14) *Aluminum Combustion under Different Condition: A Review | Journal of Energy, Mechanical, Material, and Manufacturing Engineering*. <https://ejournal.umm.ac.id/index.php/JEMMME/article/view/12550> (accessed 2024-06-08).
- (15) Gunnarsson, G.; Óskarsdóttir, G.; Frostason, S.; Magnússon, J. H. Aluminum Electrolysis with Multiple Vertical Non-Consumable Electrodes in a Low Temperature Electrolyte. In *Light Metals 2019*; Chesonis, C., Ed.; Springer International Publishing: Cham, 2019; pp 803–810. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-05864-7_98.
- (16) Eriksson, E. L. V.; Gray, E. MacA. Optimization and Integration of Hybrid Renewable Energy Hydrogen Fuel Cell Energy Systems – A Critical Review. *Appl. Energy* **2017**, *202*, 348–364. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.03.132>.
- (17) Nomura, S. Mechanism of Grain Boundary Corrosion of Aluminium in High Temperature Water. *Rev. Phys. Chem. Jpn.* **1960**, *30* (2), 100–108.
- (18) Hunter, M. S.; Fowle, P. Natural and Thermally Formed Oxide Films on Aluminum. *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **1956**, *103* (9), 482. <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.2430389>.
- (19) Meroueh, L.; Neil, L.; Eagar, T. W.; Hart, D. P. Leveraging Grain Size Effects on Hydrogen Generated via Doped Aluminum–Water Reactions Enabled by a Liquid Metal. *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* **2021**, *4* (1), 275–285. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaem.0c02175>.
- (20) Cabrera, N.; Mott, N. F. Theory of the Oxidation of Metals. *Rep. Prog. Phys.* **1949**, *12* (1), 163. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0034-4885/12/1/308>.
- (21) Cai, N.; Zhou, G.; Müller, K.; Starr, D. E. Temperature and Pressure Dependent Mott Potentials and Their Influence on Self-Limiting Oxide Film Growth. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2012**, *101* (17), 171605. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4764552>.
- (22) Fowler, J. D.; Chandra, D.; Elleman, T. S.; Payne, A. W.; Verghese, K. Tritium Diffusion in Al₂O₃ and BeO. *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* **1977**, *60* (3–4), 155–161. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1151-2916.1977.tb15493.x>.
- (23) Doremus, R. H. Diffusion in Alumina. *J. Appl. Phys.* **2006**, *100* (10), 101301. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2393012>.
- (24) Ilyin, A. P.; Mostovshchikov, A. V.; Nazarenko, O. B.; Zmanovskiy, S. V. Heat Release in Chemical Reaction between Micron Aluminum Powders and Water. *Int. J. Hydrog. Energy* **2019**, *44* (52), 28096–28103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.09.072>.
- (25) Lefèvre, G.; Duc, M.; Lepeut, P.; Caplain, R.; Fédoroff, M. Hydration of γ -Alumina in Water and Its Effects on Surface Reactivity. *Langmuir* **2002**, *18* (20), 7530–7537. <https://doi.org/10.1021/la025651i>.
- (26) Urbonavicius, M.; Varnagiris, S.; Pranevicius, L.; Milcius, D. Production of Gamma Alumina Using Plasma-Treated Aluminum and Water Reaction Byproducts. *Materials* **2020**, *13* (6), 1300. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma13061300>.
- (27) Urbonavicius, M.; Varnagiris, S.; Pranevicius, L.; Milcius, D. Production of Gamma Alumina Using Plasma-Treated Aluminum and Water Reaction Byproducts. *Materials* **2020**, *13* (6), 1300. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma13061300>.
- (28) Beck, A. F.; Heine, M. A.; Caule, E. J.; Pryor, M. J. The Kinetics of the Oxidation of Al in Oxygen at High Temperature. *Corros. Sci.* **1967**, *7* (1), 1–22. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-938X\(67\)80066-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-938X(67)80066-0).
- (29) Detailed Studies on the Flame Structure of Aluminum Particle Combustion. In *Solid Propellant Chemistry, Combustion, and Motor Interior Ballistics*; Progress in Astronautics and Aeronautics; American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, 2000; pp 689–722. <https://doi.org/10.2514/5.9781600866562.0689.0722>.
- (30) Trowell, K.; Goroshin, S.; Frost, D.; Bergthorson, J. Hydrogen Production Rates of Aluminum Reacting with Varying Densities of Supercritical Water. *RSC Adv.* **2022**, *12* (20), 12335–12343. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2ra01231f>.

- (31) Etminanbakhsh, M.; Reza Allahkaram, S. Reaction of Aluminum Particles with Superheated Steam to Generate Hydrogen Gas as a Readily Usable Clean Fuel. *Fuel* **2023**, *332*, 126011. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2022.126011>.
- (32) Il'in, A. P.; Gromov, A. A.; Vereshchagin, V. I.; Popenko, E. M.; Surgin, V. A.; Lehn, H. Combustion of Ultrafine Aluminum in Air. *Combust. Explos. Shock Waves* **2001**, *37* (6), 664–668. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1012928130644>.
- (33) *Effect of Temperature and Particle Size on Early Oxidation Characteristics of Aluminum Nanoparticles / The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*. <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jpcc.3c03073> (accessed 2024-06-21).
- (34) Alavi, S.; Thompson, D. L. Molecular Dynamics Simulations of the Melting of Aluminum Nanoparticles. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2006**, *110* (4), 1518–1523. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp053318s>.
- (35) Li, G.; Yang, H.-X.; Yuan, C.-M.; Eckhoff, R. K. A Catastrophic Aluminium-Alloy Dust Explosion in China. *J. Loss Prev. Process Ind.* **2016**, *39*, 121–130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jlp.2015.11.013>.
- (36) Li, L.; Xu, K.; Yao, X.; Chen, S. Probabilistic Analysis of Aluminium Production Explosion Accidents Based on a Fuzzy Bayesian Network. *J. Loss Prev. Process Ind.* **2021**, *73*, 104618. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jlp.2021.104618>.
- (37) Donohue, M. D.; Aranovich, G. L. Classification of Gibbs Adsorption Isotherms. *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.* **1998**, *76–77*, 137–152. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0001-8686\(98\)00044-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0001-8686(98)00044-X).
- (38) Clausen, E. M.; Hren, J. J. The Gamma to Alpha Transformation in Thin Film Alumina. *MRS Online Proc. Libr. OPL* **1984**, *41*, 381. <https://doi.org/10.1557/PROC-41-381>.
- (39) Beccat, P.; Silva, P. D.; Huiban, Y.; Kasztelan, S. Quantitative Surface Analysis by Xps (X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy): Application to Hydrotreating Catalysts. *Oil Gas Sci. Technol.* **1999**, *54* (4), 487–496. <https://doi.org/10.2516/ogst:1999042>.
- (40) *The study of the volume expansion of aluminum during porous oxide formation at galvanostatic regime - ScienceDirect*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S016943320301016X?via%3Dihub> (accessed 2024-06-09).
- (41) Bhatia, S. K.; Perlmutter, D. D. A random pore model for fluid-solid reactions: I. Isothermal, kinetic control. *AIChE J.* **1980**, *26* (3), 379–386. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aic.690260308>.
- (42) Marbán, G. Correct Use of the Bhatia and Perlmutter Random Pore Model under Nonisothermal Conditions. *ACS Omega* **2024**, *9* (9), 10793–10798. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.3c09755>.

Appendix:

TABLE 5: EXPERIMENTS - LOW CONVERSION (0-20% H₂ GENERATION).

Al-Fuel	T (°C)	p (bar)	t (h)	Conversion (% H ₂)
Al-10Si	350	1	2	0,0%
Al-10Si	400	1	3	0,0%
Al-10Si	500	1	6	0,0%
Al-10Si	500	Variable (40-45)	2,5	0,0%
Al-10Si	Variable (300-350)	1	6	0,0%
Al-10Si		1	6	0,0%
Al-10Si				0,0%
Al-10Si	500	1	98	0,7%
Al-CutWire1.0mm	550	45	6	17,3%
Al-CutWire1.2mm	550	46	6	14,5%
Al-Foil	200	2		0,0%
Al-Foil	500	1		0,0%
Al-Foil	500	4		0,0%
Al-Foil	500	10	15	0,0%
Al-Foil	500	10		0,0%
Al-Foil	500 (heat source off after start)	30		0,0%
Al-Foil	450	1	6	0,1%
Al-Foil	450	5	6	0,1%
Al-Foil	500	1	6	0,4%
Al-Foil	450	10	6	0,4%
Al-Foil	500	5	6	0,5%
Al-Foil	500	10	3	0,8%
Al-Foil	550	1	6	0,8%
Al-Foil	400	40		0,8%
Al-Foil	500	10	6	1,0%
Al-Foil	500	1	60	1,2%
Al-Foil	550	5	6	1,2%
Al-Foil	500 (heat source off after start)	30	1	1,3%
Al-Foil	550	10	6	2,0%
Al-Foil	500	1	24	2,3%
Al-Foil	300	40	2	2,4%
Al-Foil	300	42	6	2,6%
Al-Foil	500	10	21	2,6%
Al-Foil	300	40	1,5	9,1%
Al-Foil	550	17	6	10,0%
Al-Foil	550	18	3,5	10,8%
Al-Foil	550	17	6	11,7%
Al-Krampe	550	41	6	7,2%
Al-Krampe	550	48	7	16,3%
Al-PC20	Variable			0,0%
Al-PC20 (Mix with Al-10Si)	Variable (250-300-350-400)	1	48	10,5%
Al-Rounded0.8mm	550	45	6	0,0%
Al-Rounded1.0mm	550	43	6	10,6%
Al-Spajic-1.6	Variable (400-500-550)	Variable (40-45)	5,5	17,8%

TABLE 6: EXPERIMENTS - MEDIUM CONVERSION (20-80% H₂ GENERATION)

Al-Fuel	T (°C)	p (bar)	t (h)	Conversion (% H ₂)
Al-CutWire0.6mm	550	47	6	40,9%
Al-CutWire0.8mm	550	48	6	23,0%
Al-Foil	250	40	6	23,9%
Al-Foil	500	29	1	30,5%
Al-Foil	500 (heat source off after start)	30	1,5	31,3%
Al-Foil	500	17	6	37,6%
Al-Foil	500	17	6	39,0%
Al-Foil	450	18	6	54,8%
Al-Foil	500	30		55,5%
Al-Krampe	550	47	4	25,4%
Al-Krampe	550	45	5,5	25,5%
Al-Krampe	Variable (500-550)	Variable (40-45)	6	71,1%
Al-Krampe	550	46	6,5	75,3%
Al-Krampe	550	46	6	75,6%
Al-Spajic-1.6	550	45	6	21,4%

FIGURE 55: MEDIUM CONVERSION (20-80% H₂ GENERATION) - AL-CUTWIRE.

FIGURE 56: MEDIUM CONVERSION (20-80% H₂ GENERATION) - AL-FOIL.

FIGURE 57: MEDIUM CONVERSION (20-80% H₂ GENERATION) - AL-KRAMPE.

FIGURE 58: MEDIUM CONVERSION (20-80% H₂ GENERATION) - AL-SPAJIC1.6.

TABLE 3: EXPERIMENTS - HIGH CONVERSION (80+% H₂ GENERATION).

AL-FUEL	T (°C)	P (BAR)	T (H)	CONVERSION (% H2)
AL-CUTWIRE0.6MM	550	47	6	89,6%
AL-CUTWIRE0.8MM	550	45	6	86,2%
AL-DECO	550	40	3,5	93,8%
AL-FOIL	550	29	6	81,0%
AL-FOIL	550	27	6	82,3%
AL-FOIL	450	28	6	89,6%
AL-FOIL	500	41	3	90,8%
AL-FOIL	500	30	4	92,3%
AL-FOIL	500	29	5,5	92,8%
AL-FOIL	500	28	4,5	93,8%
AL-FOIL	500	29	3	95,5%
AL-FOIL	500	28	5	96,2%
AL-FOIL	500	30	6	97,0%
AL-FOIL	500	VARIABLE (30-40)	4,5	99,8%
AL-FOIL	350	40	2	100,0%
AL-FOIL	500 (HEAT SOURCE OFF AFTER START)	30	3,5	100,0%
AL-FOIL	500	29	5	100,0%
AL-ROUNDED0.6MM	550	45	6	82,3%

FIGURE 59: HIGH CONVERSION (80+% H₂ GENERATION) - AL CUTWIRE

FIGURE 60: HIGH CONVERSION (80+% H₂ GENERATION) - AL-DECO.

FIGURE 61: HIGH CONVERSION (80+% H₂ GENERATION) - AL-FOIL.

FIGURE 62: HIGH CONVERSION (80+% H₂ GENERATION) - AL-ROUNDED.

FIGURE 63: HIGH CONVERSION (80+% H₂ GENERATION) - AL-FOIL - REPEATABILITY OF EXPERIMENTS.

At reaction conditions of 500°C and 30 bar, all experiments using Al-Foil as a fuel source result in high conversion within 3 to 6 h.